

obtained and not the expected products **4d, f-k** and **5d, f-k**. The physical and spectral data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Blich apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were carried out on a Coleman analyser. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 720 and 257 spectrophotometers and pmr spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO-d₆) on Varian A-60D and Jeol FX-90 spectrometers using TMS as internal standard.

Substituted dihydropyrazolones (1): 2,4-Dihydro-2-benzyl-5-methyl-3H-pyrazol-3-one³, 2,4-dihydro-2,5-diphenyl-3H-pyrazol-3-one⁴ and 2,4-dihydro-2-(2'-benzothiazolyl)-5-methyl-3H-pyrazol-3-one⁵ were prepared by known methods.

4-Arylideno-2,4-dihydro-2,5-disubstituted-3H-pyrazol-3-ones (3) and 4,4'-arylmethylene-bis-(2,4-dihydro-2,5-disubstituted-3H-pyrazol-3-ones (4): A mixture of the dihydropyrazolone (**1**; 0.01 mol) and the aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10–15 ml) was heated for 15 min and left overnight at room temperature. The 4-arylidene derivative (**3**) separated as coloured crystals, was dried and recrystallised from benzene. If no crystals appeared at this stage, a small amount of water was added till slight turbidity appeared and the mixture was allowed to stand to give coloured crystals of **3**.

To the mother liquor a sufficient amount of water was added to yield compound **4** which was dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

4,4'-Arylmethylene-bis-(1,3-disubstituted-5-hydroxy-1H-pyrazole) (5): To a mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) dissolved in absolute ethanol (50 ml), piperidine (10–12 drops) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and kept at room temperature. The resulting crystals were dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Antifungal activity: All the compounds (Table 1) were evaluated for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and *A. niger* at three concentrations, viz., 10, 100 and 1000 ppm by employing food poisoning of solidified agar technique⁶. The average (of three replications) percentage inhibition after 96 h was determined and the results were compared with those obtained using the commercial fungicide orthophaltan (W.P. 50%). The results indicated that 2-(2'-benzothiazolyl)-4-arylideno-pyrazolones (**3g-k**) caused complete inhibition or almost so, of the both the fungi at 1000 ppm concentration similar to orthophaltan. But at lower doses, the observed fungitoxicities were considerably lower than those observed with orthophaltan. It is noteworthy that the introduction of the dimethylamino group in the aryl moiety of the compounds (**3d, f, j**) enhances the fungitoxicity to some extent. Thus the presence of benzothiazolyl and dimethylamino groups together in compound (**3j**) have contributed to its better antifungal potency. It was also observed from the

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some 4-Arylmethylene Derivatives of Substituted Pyrazolones

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2,4-Dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one and its derivatives possess various biological activities¹. In view of this, we have synthesised the title compounds for achieving fungicides of better potency.

The condensation² of 2,4-dihydro-2-benzyl-5-methyl-3H-pyrazol-3-ones (**1**) and aromatic aldehydes (**2**), in glacial acetic acid led to the formation of the corresponding 4-arylidene derivatives (**3a-c, e**) and 4,4'-arylmethylene-bis-(2,4-dihydro-2,5-disubstituted-3H-pyrazol-3-ones) (**4a-c, e**). The condensation compounds **1** and **2** in alkaline condition (piperidine) yielded 4,4'-arylmethylene-bis-(1,3-disubstituted-5-hydroxy-1H-pyrazoles) (**5a-c, e**) (Scheme 1).

When the condensation was carried out either with *p*-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)benzaldehyde (**d, f, j**) or using 2-(2'-benzothiazolyl)pyrazolones (**1g-k**) in both acidic and basic media separately, only the corresponding arylidene derivatives (**3d, f-k**) were

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Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	δ^{**}
3a	16-37	15	1 670s (C=O), 1 590s (C=N)	1.95 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.83 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.10-8.00 (11H, m, 10ArH and one olefinic proton)
3b	170-72	12	1 690, 1 500	2.21 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.86 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.20-8.30 (10H, m, 9ArH and one olefinic proton)
3c	157	20	1 675, 1 605	2.18 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.92 (2H, s, CH ₂), 6.90-8.60 (10H, m, 9ArH and one olefinic proton)
3d	178-80	80	1 660, 1 580	2.20 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.10 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 4.94 (2H, s, CH ₂), 6.65-8.61 (10H, m, 9ArH and one olefinic proton)
3e	144-45	11	1 670, 1 605	2.22 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.88 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.20-9.15 (10H, m, 9ArH and one olefinic proton)
3f	140-41	70	1 675, 1 580	3.12 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 6.67 (1H, s, one olefinic proton), 6.76-8.58 (14H, m, ArH)
3g	210-12	65	1 640, 1 520	—
3h	198-200	58	1 630, 1 500	—
3i	187-88	69	1 675, 1 570	2.37 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.80-8.50 (9H, m, 8ArH and one olefinic proton)
3j	270-72	83	1 675, 1 560	2.43 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.15 (6H, s, NMe ₂), 6.70-8.60 (9H, m, 8ArH and one olefinic proton)
3k	190-92	54	1 630, 1 500	—

NOTES

(Table 1 Contd.)

4a	188-89	60	2 800-2 500, 1 840-1 680	1.90 (6H, s, 2×CH ₃), 4.71 (4H, s, 2×CH ₂), 4.63 (1H, s, CH), 7.10-7.50 (15H, m, ArH), 12.90 (2H, bs, D ₂ O exchangeable 2×NH)
4b	225-26	55	2 800-2 400, 1 860-1 680	2.31 (6H, s, 2×CH ₃), 5.02 (5H, bs, 2×CH ₂ and one CH), 7.11-8.12 (16H, m, 2H D ₂ O exchangeable, 14×ArH and 2×NH)
4c	193-95	30	2 800-2 500, 1 840-1 680	1.88 (6H, s, 2×CH ₃), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.64 (1H, s, CH), 4.76 (4H, s, 2×CH ₂), 6.74-7.24 (16H, m, 2H D ₂ O exchangeable, 14×ArH and 2×NH)
4e	205-206	45	2 800-2 500, 1 840-1 660	1.70 (6H, s, 2×CH ₃), 5.00 (5H, bs, 2×CH ₂ and CH), 6.60-8.00 (14H, m, ArH), 12.70 (2H, bs, D ₂ O exchangeable, 2×NH).
5a	179-80	15	2 750, 2 625, 2 550, 2 450 _{vw} (NH) 1 600 _s (C=N)	
5b	185-87	35	2 770, 2 700, 2 590, 2 500, 1 595	
5c	175-77	20	2 770, 2 660, 2 560, 2 460, 1 590	
5e	180-81	30	2 770, 2 700, 2 590, 2 560, 1 590	

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **Recorded in CDCl₃, except 4b (DMSO-d₆) compounds 3g, 3h, 3k, 5a-c and 5e insoluble in CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆.

screening data that, in general, compounds 4a-c, e and 5a-c, e are more toxic to both the fungi than the compounds 3a-c, e. Thus it is quite evident that as the number of biolabile pyrazole nuclei is increased in the compound, the fungitoxicity is enhanced accordingly.

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